

Milestone MS17

Preliminary Design of a Federated Network for Methodologies in Ocean Observing

Funded by
the European Union

MILESTONE

Milestone	MS17 Preliminary Design of a federated network for methodologies in Ocean Observing
Due Date	28 February 2025
Submission Date	27 February 2025
Milestone Lead	Jay Pearlman (IEEE) Pauline Simpson (IEEE)
Work packages involved	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5
Authors	Jay Pearlman (IEEE) jay.pearlman@ieee.org and Pauline Simpson (IEEE) paulinesimpson@ieee.org
Contributing Authors	El Khalil Cherif (IEEE) Fehmi Dilmahamod (GEOMAR) Johannes Karstensen (GEOMAR) Antonio Novellino (ETT) Beatrice Scotto (ETT) Steffen M. Olsen (DMI) Sabrina Speich (ENS) Alessandra Onida (ENS) Athanasia Papapostolou (HCMR) Lasse H. Pettersson (NERSC)
External co-authors	Justin Buck (NOC) Cristian Munoz Mas (IMR)
Copyright License	CC BY 4.0 https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reviewer	Chiara Bearzotti (DMI)

DISCLAIMER

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abbreviations	4
1. Means of verification	5
2. What is this Milestone about?	5
3. Objectives and Requirements	6
3.1 Objectives of OPFN	6
3.2 Requirements of OPFN	9
4. Framework for OPFN: an evolution of OBPS	11
4.1 OPFN Conceptual Framework/Structure	11
4.2. OPFN comparison with OBPS	12
5. OPFN System Architecture/Design Concept	13
5.1 OPFN Architecture Concept	13
5.2 Design Approach and Process	14
5.3 Roadmap for developing OPFN	17
6. Recommendations and Summary	18
7. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives	19
8. References	20

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BP	Best Practices
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EBV	Essential Biological Variable
EC	European Commission
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
EDS	Enhanced Discovery System
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
IT	Information Technology
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LLM	Large Language Model
MMS	Methodological Management Systems
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System
OIH	Ocean Info Hub

OPFN	Ocean Practices Federated Network
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SO4	ObsSea4Clim Strategic Objective 4
UI	User Interface
UNESCO-IOC	United National Educational, Cultural and Science Organisation - Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

1. Means of verification

As stated in the Description of the Action, the means to verify that this Milestone has been achieved is the following: “Preliminary Design Summary provided to partners by Task 2.2”.

2. What is this Milestone about?

This Milestone provides a list of requirements, a framework, a conceptual design and a roadmap for the implementation of the **Ocean Practices Federated Network (OPFN)**. Key items in each element are given. The **OPFN** will be a crucial response to the need for global access and adoption of standardized methodologies for understanding, forecasting and managing oceans with a focus on climate processes and impacts. Both the cultural and technical aspects are identified to facilitate broader acceptance of best practice creation and use. The implementation should be straightforward with the early steps of community engagement and working with potential partners being the highest near-term priority.

The OPFN builds on the experience over the last decade with the Ocean Best Practices System (www.oceanbestpractices.org). It is different from the OBPS, which is a repository global collection in a single archive. OPFN is a network of repositories where

each repository maintains the currency of its collection and is a focal point for the community it serves. In this way, a broad range of communities can be effectively engaged. A more detailed comparison is provided in Section 4.2 of this Milestone.

In this document, “practices” includes both practices and standards (Pearlman, et al, 2019) and the general term “practices” is used. The document also uses the generally used term “best practice” for a variety of practices maturities, which may be classed as emerging, good, better or best practices (Mantovani, et al., 2024)

This Milestone describes how best practices and standards underpin and provide the building blocks for marine monitoring and understanding the ocean physical environment. It offers an OPFN solution for the present limited access to the fragmented collections of practices and standards worldwide, which is restricting the pace of advancement towards an interoperable ocean data ecosystem.

The OPFN will build on the foundation of the [Ocean Best Practices System \(OBPS\)](#). The OPFN and the OBPS have similar goals for supporting access to high-quality ocean information for research, environmental and climate assessments, applications, impact models, and policy. The OBPS is a repository collecting and storing practices from across the globe in its archive. The OPFN will unite distributed and independent systems by interoperably cross-linking the holdings of regional and global platforms. See Section 4.2 for a more detailed comparison.

3. Objectives and Requirements

3.1 Objectives of OPFN

Originating from the expressed needs of the ocean sciences community, OPFN aims to streamline, through a single comprehensive FAIR (Wilkinson, et al, 2016) and [CARE](#)-compliant platform. This will enhance the transparency for discovery, access, comparison, and application of distributed and diverse methodologies. OPFN’s metadata standards, open-access framework, and user control features reflect key FAIR

Principles, enabling interoperability and transparency. Future iterations of OPFN will further strengthen these alignments by incorporating user-driven feedback and evolving data-sharing policies. A key attribute is that the OPFN System will allow organisations, programmes, networks, as well as projects and other short-term initiatives to preserve, organize, and track the re-use and sharing of their methodological know-how.

The system objectives and its design requirements are generally considered in two groups. “Cultural aspects” are called *non-functional characteristics* of a system. They describe user requirements, how the system should perform, its attributes, quality and limitations. The *functional characteristics* are the features of the system that include tasks and operations. Non-functional requirements drive the technical architecture of a system (Adams, 2015). Functional requirements drive the application architecture of a system. Fig. 1 provides features of a design approach for functional and non-functional characteristics. These are broad features. Details of these characteristics for ocean applications are given in Section 3.2

Fig. 1: Attributes of a system's functional and non-functional requirements (Geeks, 2025)

Cultural Perspective - a discussion of non-functional objectives

A key OPFN objective is to drive a cultural shift towards global sharing and adoption of best practices among diverse ocean communities leading to consistent observational techniques and data management methods. To meet this objective, users must have access to a range of practices and also to information for selecting the most appropriate practice. The Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) offers users opportunities for informed selection decisions. An example of these steps is the definition of a maturity model (Mantovani, et al, 2024), which makes it easier to determine if practices are either good, better or best practices. An endorsement process has been introduced (Bushnell & Pearlman, 2024; Hermes, 2020) to identify those practices recommended by Expert Panels. Also, the OBPS repository provides the number of downloads for each single practice, thus indicating which practices are of more interest. These attributes will also be part of the OPFN requirements.

Technical Perspective - a discussion of functional objectives.

From a technical perspective, OPFN will leverage rapidly evolving digital technologies supporting the single-point discovery of ocean observation methods whilst maintaining distributed content access. Typically, functional objectives are an operational system with software that is easy to use. For the OPFN, the system also needs to support a wide range of discovery criteria, so that a user can look for practices that are relevant to their needs, e.g. looking for EOV, Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), Endorsement or Maturity. A third objective is to have a framework so that OPFN nodes can join the system, bringing their own ocean domain experience to OPFN.

Other technical objectives include making designs capable of cloud basing and portability. Scalability is needed as nodes join OPFN. Experience has shown that users strongly prefer a system that is sustained, so system sustainability is another objective. Finally, the system must accommodate policy changes. For example, the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) impacted operations relating to user authentication and retained information security.

In summary, the design must provide a sustained system which supports the user and product needs defined in the non-functional requirements.

3.2 Requirements of OPFN

As discussed above, functional objectives guide the system's technical requirements. Non-functional requirements specify overall characteristics such as cost, user experience and reliability (Adams, 2015). Generally, functional requirements are expressed in the form "system must do <requirement>," while non-functional requirements take the form "system shall be <requirement>" (Loucopoulos, 2005). The OPFN system functional requirements are for an open and adaptable framework to support technology evolution, particularly relating to emerging Information Technology (IT) including, for example, advances in storage, cloud environments and artificial intelligence. Finally, sustainability and cost for evolution and operations (future-proofing) need to be considered.

To achieve its objectives, the OPFN will need to meet the following non-functional and functional requirements. These lists are expected to evolve with the detailed design and implementation of the OPFN through collaboration with the end users and participating nodes (co-design).

Non-Functional Requirements, provided in the recommended order

- Operation of a permanent, sustainable archive
- Follows FAIR/CARE principles
- Supports TRUST principles¹
- Easy/intuitive/simple to user interface with a low barrier to entry for users
- Robust search logic
- Identifiers for practices: DOI, ISBN, ISSN, Other
- On-screen help text and user training for using OPFN including training videos and user guides

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-020-0486-7> (Lin, et al, (2020)

- Multi-format and object types including multimedia (video, audio, documents)
- Multi-language content with on-demand (automated) translation capabilities
- Automated citation generation and citation export
- Monitoring and automated generation of robust metrics of access to practices
- Accommodate a full range of practices from observations, data, and modelling to applications and policy
- Rights Permission (for IP)
- Meet global web accessibility regulations²
- Detailed metadata available to users
- Search by practice characteristics – e.g., maturity, endorsement, relevant EOV
- Feedback/communication loops to BP creators and users including surveys
- Linkage for practice dependencies
- Linking practices with the datasets produced by using them
- Identification of relevant geographic areas and disciplines for practices identified

Functional Requirements, provided in the recommended order

- Search engine layout, structure, User Interface (UI) elements, and navigation elements repurposed from existing capabilities (such as OBPS) and community-supported software whenever possible
- Sustainability in design and operation including provision for evolution
- A system capable of operating on a dedicated platform or in the Cloud
- Software should be transportable (dockerized) to move between platforms
- Support diverse user platforms (desktop, mobile, etc)
- Robust design which avoids single-point failures
- Content of the search results given in the UI including a link to the provider (node) content access
- Use of AI, LLMs, natural language, semantic indexing for search and indicative summarization of multiple practices

² https://european-union.europa.eu/web-accessibility-policy_en

- Metrics for practice viewing, practice downloads and general use.
- Version Control with links between versions
- Usability and Web Accessibility
- Graphical interfaces (e.g. viewing the geographic applicability of a practice)
- Ability to save search strategy and implement RSS feeds
- Capability for user help desk and training for OPFN use.
- Support for user feedback for the system and for the practices accessed.

4. Framework for OPFN: an evolution of OBPS

4.1 OPFN Conceptual Framework/Structure

Supporting the above requirements, key system attributes for an OPFN framework have been identified. These include:

Key Characteristics of an OPFN Framework:

1. **Reusable:** can be used across applications with minimal modification.
2. **Portability:** can be operated on multiple types of platforms
3. **Inversion of Control (IoC):** can call both codes and functions at specific points for processing.
4. **Predefined Structure:** offers a skeleton or blueprint for organizing and implementing solutions.
5. **Common structure:** supports consistency in metadata, software tools and visualization (UI).
6. **Extensible:** allows developers to extend and customize components while adhering to its structure.
7. **Evolution:** provides adaptability for evolving technologies
8. **User and Web Accessibility:** provides authentications and other related support services

4.2. OPFN comparison with OBPS

As mentioned briefly in Section 2 above, the OPFN and the OBPS have similar goals for supporting access to high-quality ocean information for research, environmental and climate assessments, applications, impact models and policy. While the objectives are similar, the approaches for providing the services are somewhat different. For example, OPFN's federated model ensures regional autonomy while maintaining global interoperability. OBPS, as a central repository, sustains access to practices that do not have an organizational repository or are placed on a website, but do not have a permanent home. Table 1 provides a high-level comparison of the framework elements of both systems. The OPFN characteristics are defined from the requirements of Section 3 above. Much of the experience over a decade with OBPS carries over to the OPFN design.

OPFN	OBPS
Federation of distributed cross-discipline repositories (one of them may be OBPS)	A centralized repository focused on ocean-related science and applications
Applies the FAIR and CARE Principles	Applies the FAIR and CARE Principles
Single search across globally distributed multiple methodological collections	Single search across the methodological collection in OBPS (>2200 at present)
A collaborative community of best practices repositories	A unified best practices repository
New Co-Design to introduce a collaborative network framework	Enhancements to an existing operational design
OPFN will share governance with a network of organizations	OBPS is an organization within the UNESCO IOC.
Quality control processes are done by data and Information professionals	Quality control processes are done by data and Information professionals
Search interface only	Separate Search and Submission interfaces

Currency of content: nodes will ensure the most recent versions are available in their collections for harvest by OPFN	OBPS works with practice submitters and repository managers to maintain currency
Opportunity to standardize and use agreed best practices document templates across all the communities	OBPS Best Practice Document templates available to ocean community
JSON-LD schema.org metadata convention	Qualified Dublin Core and JSON-LD metadata convention
In an operational phase, OPFN metadata schema will accommodate rich metadata	OBPS has existing rich metadata schema including EOV/ECV/EBV/ SDG etc, provides comprehensive description and robust discovery and access
Users access a practice document only from the node source (maintains the source metrics)	Users can access the full text document in OBPS and OBPS also provides the original document source URI/DOI
Does not include institutions and organizations without methodological collections	Supports all organisations and active people in creating and or using common practices for their work

Table 1: High-Level Comparison of OPFN and OBPS

5. OPFN System Architecture/Design Concept

5.1 OPFN Architecture Concept

The architecture concept is built around nodes hosted by organisations with methodological collections in their repositories (see Fig. 2). The methods metadata from each node is converted by the node into a common schema.org format following the OPFN technical specifications for metadata exchange. The metadata is collected in an OPFN database to support methods discovery requests from OPFN users. In addition to the node’s metadata, the nodes make copies of their stored methods documents available to OPFN to allow for a full-text search on OPFN. These methods documents are not for user consumption; user access to the full-text document is

through the node's own repository. For content access, the user is linked to the node repository through the OPFN user interface portal.

The user interface (OPFN UI) provides single-point access to the entire federated network. The search will allow user-selected filters which help the user find practices related to topics such as EOVS relevance, author, or maturity. Once a method of interest is discovered, the user is directed to the appropriate node to gain access to the entire document. The current OPFN approach is for nodes to maintain and deliver practices that are open, ideally following the FAIR and CARE principles. Users may also access the nodes directly through the node's own portal.

Fig. 2: OPFN Architecture Concept: Nodes convert metadata to schema.org format for centralized discovery. Users access full documents via node repositories, preserving source metrics.

5.2 Design Approach and Process

The conceptual design (Fig. 3) focuses on the information flow within OPFN and the expected outcomes responding to the non-functional and functional requirements.

The flow is defined through a stakeholder-centric design approach in which the nodes contribute their guidance toward the design, complementing user inputs for OPFN. The processes needed for an effective and sustainable network are identified in this synergistic environment. These processes must allow for both network operations and the standardized approaches to methodological management of individual repositories or subnetworks. This is done in the context of a framework and architecture with common conventions and the use of standardized elements such as vocabularies, metadata conventions (e.g. schema.org), community assessment tools such as maturity models and endorsement and information technology tools such as large language models (LLM) and artificial intelligence (AI).

Fig. 3: Elements of the OPFN design.

Design Process

The schematic for the design process is shown in Fig. 4.

There are underlying assumptions for this process to be successful. Nodes will format their metadata into the extended OPFN format. They will ultimately have maturity assessments of their practices and quality metrics in the method descriptions to allow for more effective and efficient searches. They may consider being a centre for method endorsement.

Community engagement, particularly with users, is essential. Monitoring of use and other metrics will be built into the system. Also, a user service capability (help desk) and, more generally, user support (including training) will be a core OPFN offering. Such capabilities will be refined in an OPFN detailed design.

Fig. 4: OPFN Process Design; MMS: methodological management system; EDS: enhanced discovery system; ODIS OIH: Ocean InfoHub; ODIS-Arch: Ocean Data and Information System architecture.

5.3 Roadmap for developing OPFN

This section illustrates the evolution of key elements for the OPFN development with a suggested roadmap for implementing the OPFN. The roadmap builds on the concepts, requirements, and preliminary design elements outlined above. The roadmap is organized into phases and tasks (see Table 2). The first three phases are development and the last is operations. An initial pilot demonstration will operate with a subset of the comprehensive metadata as nodes build their knowledge base to address the full capability. Based on experience, the steps for implementation should be straightforward and the early steps of community engagement and working with potential partners are the highest near-term priority. This would use a co-design approach described in a UNESCO IOC GOOS UN Ocean Decade Action. Several of the existing and emerging networks will be engaged including the ObsSea4Clim stakeholder network, the European EOVS network, GOOS OCG and regional networks, selected organization steering committees such as OBPS, GOOS and IODE of the IOC and European organizations including EuroGOOS, EC-OBPSS, OceanPractices AISBL and EMODnet. This effort is part of ObsSea4Clim WP2, Task 2.2 and will be done in coordination with other ObsSea4Clim work packages particularly WP6 for dissemination and user engagement.

Phase	Objective	Tasks
Phase 1: Preparation and Stakeholder Engagement	Establish foundational requirements, secure buy-in from key stakeholders, and confirm alignment with existing systems (e.g., OBPS).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Refine Scope and Governance ● Stakeholder and Community Consultation ● Requirements Consolidation ● Planning & Resource Identification
Phase 2: Architectural Design and Prototype Development	Finalize the OPFN reference architecture, data flows, metadata schema alignment, and develop a proof-of-concept prototype.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OPFN Reference Architecture ● Metadata Standards and Ontology Alignment ● Prototype (Alpha) Development ● Testing and Feedback
Phase 3: Pilot Implementation and Iteration	Onboard additional repositories, refine functionalities, e.g., advanced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scaling the Federation (additional Pilot Nodes)

	search, maturity model, endorsement and ensure robust user mechanisms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Functionalities • Community Capacity Building • Refinement Cycles
Phase 4: Full Operational Capability and Consolidation	Achieve full deployment, sustainability, and global adoption of OPFN.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full Operational Release • Sustainability Planning • Monitoring, Metrics, and Continuous Improvement • International Endorsement and Promotion

Table 2: OPFN implementation plan

6. Recommendations and Summary

The Ocean Practices Federated Network (OPFN) offers a significant advance in access to methods from a broad spectrum of ocean research and applications. It is a paradigm shift for users by providing a single point access for methods of initially physical oceanography with potential for extension to all ocean disciplines.

The OPFN requirements and concept design are built on a decade of experience with the OBPS. Significant outcomes of the OPFN will include:

- Enhanced collaboration and knowledge sharing
- Improved interoperability and information exchange
- Established mechanisms for broader adoption of Best Practices
- Enhanced stakeholder proficiency and engagement.

This Milestone MS17 report provides requirements, a framework, a conceptual design and a roadmap for the implementation of the OPFN. Both the requirements for cultural and technical aspects are identified to facilitate broader acceptance of best practice creation and use. The implementation steps, guided by Task 2.4, will engage ObsSea4Clim networks (e.g., Stakeholder network, European EOVS network, etc) for user guidance as part of a co-design effort.

An important recommendation from this Milestone is that the evolution and operation of the OPFN be supported across Europe through the engagement of methodological repositories at both the regional and national levels. To extend the developments beyond ObsSea4Clim, the European Commission may consider looking at policies to stimulate and sustain engagement and a targeted Coordination and Support Action to energise the fragmented and diverse organizations to participate in an OPFN integrated system.

7. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

Below is a summary of how the Ocean Practices Federated Network (OPFN) directly supports and contributes to the ObsSea4Clim objectives, particularly Strategic Objective 4 (SO4). The emphasis is on strengthening interoperability and best-practice adoption across the physical oceanography.

SO4	<p>To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing</p>
<p>This Milestone MS17 document offers an approach to expand the availability of best practices through the creation of an OPFN. This addresses two challenges. The first and foremost challenge is to bring the presently distributed methodological collections into one standardized system. The second challenge is the governance and management of a worldwide and scalable system. The activities identified in this Milestone are complemented by other activities in ObsSea4Clim WP2 (e.g., best practice alignment with EOV/ECV, maturity assessment and alignment of best practices and standards with EOV/ECV specification sheets). The OPFN, along with the OBPS, is a foundation for expanding the creation and adoption of best practices.</p>	

OPFN directly supports SO4 by federating methodologies for ECV/EOV alignment, enabling access to practices for satellite and in-situ data interoperability.

8. References

Adams, K.M. (2015) Definitions for Functional and Non-Functional Requirements. In: *Non-functional Requirements in Systems Analysis and Design*. Springer. pp. 45–50.

DOI:[10.1007/978-3-319-18344-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-18344-2)

Bushnell, Mark and Pearlman, Jay (eds) (2024) *Ocean Best Practices System Endorsement: Guidance for the Ocean Community, Version 2024-03-20*. Ocean Best Practices System, 8pp. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25607/OBP-1983>

CARE Principles. Available: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>. (Accessed 31 January 2025)

European Union Web Accessibility Policy. Available: https://european-union.europa.eu/web-accessibility-policy_en. (Accessed 31 January 2025)

Geeks for Geeks (2025) Functional vs. Non-Functional Requirements. Available: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/functional-vs-non-functional-requirements/>. (Accessed 31 January 2025)

Hermes, J. (ed.) (2020) *GOOS Best Practices Endorsement Process*. Paris, France, Global Ocean Observing System, 7pp. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-926>

Loucopoulos, P. (2005) Requirements Engineering. In: Clarkson J, & Eckert C (eds.). *Design Process Improvement: A Review of Current Practice*. Springer-Verlag. pp. 116–139. DOI:[10.1007/978-1-84628-061-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-84628-061-0)

Mantovani, C., Pearlman, J., Rubio, A., Przeslawski, R., Bushnell, M., Simpson, P., Cognati L., Alvarez, E., Cosoli, S. and Roarty, H. (2024) An ocean practices maturity model: from good to best practices. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 11:1415374, 19pp. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2024.1415374>

Pearlman, Jay, Bushnell, Mark, Coppola, Laurent, Karstensen, Johannes, Buttigieg, Pier Luigi, Pearlman, Françoise, Simpson, Pauline, et al (2019) Evolving and Sustaining Ocean Best Practices and Standards for the Next Decade. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6:277, 19pp. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00277>

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3: 160018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

